

Management of Levonorgestrel and Etonogestrel Adsorption to Polypropylene During In Vitro Release from Long-acting Release Dosage Forms

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ABSTRACT

Adsorption of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) to various surfaces of labware can skew data during drug development. We observed substantial loss of two clinically significant hydrophobic contraceptive steroids, levonorgestrel (LNG) and etonogestrel (ENG), during in vitro release evaluation from poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA) microspheres and microneedles, leading to incomplete drug recovery. Our investigation identified adsorption of these APIs to polypropylene (PP) as a key factor adversely affecting both the drug loss and sensitivity/linearity of UPLC-UV assays during in vitro release tests. Furthermore, LC-MS/MS plasma assays showed improved accuracy and reduced variability when calibration curves were prepared in glass vials instead of PP vials. Adsorption was also observed in simple PP pipette tips in standard aqueous solutions. To address the adsorption and mass loss, we found that adding acetonitrile to samples after they were collected from glass in vitro release vessels effectively mitigated mass loss. The presence of plasticizers, such as diisononyl adipate found in common porous nylon bags used to contain PLGA dosage forms, was shown to reduce LNG/ENG adsorption to PP. In addition, atomic force microscopy provided experimental characterization of the drug solution-PP/glass interface, showing a higher surface area of the PP surface from nanostructures and an increase in adhesion force with LNG molecules. A thorough understanding and mitigation of API adsorption, including selection of appropriate apparatus materials and considering the possible role of contamination from plasticizers and other leachables, is important for the accurate development of analytical assays supporting pharmaceutical development of long-acting contraceptives.

1. Introduction

Sorption of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) to utility consumables like tubes, vials, and molds made of polyvinylchloride (PVC), polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), and polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) is frequently observed in pre-clinical and clinical stages of drug development¹⁻⁸. In addition, the interaction of APIs such as steroids with pharmaceutical materials such as IV bags is well known to remove drug before administration, decreasing the actual dose delivered^{3,9,10}. The mass loss due to drug adsorption can also result in misinterpretation of data if researchers were unaware of the phenomenon. Specifically in pharmaceutical formulation development, *in vitro* release experiments and *in vivo* pharmacokinetic studies are performed to evaluate the performance of a formulation regarding release kinetics, *in vitro-in vivo* correlations, and safety. API adsorption during *in vitro* release studies may be misinterpreted as slow and incomplete drug release due to failure of the formulation strategy. Research on the adsorption of APIs to utility consumables, though sporadic over the last decades, may help avoid misinterpretation of experimental data and develop robust analytical assays for accurate formulation development and analysis of product quality.

Levonorgestrel (LNG) and etonogestrel (ENG) are widely used contraceptive steroids that have been formulated into oral tablets as well as implantable devices¹¹⁻¹⁴. They are also being actively formulated into more-advanced, long-acting, controlled-release systems such as microparticles (MPs) and microneedles (MNs). Development of these new biodegradable polymer controlled-release systems for contraceptive hormones address the strong and still unmet need to further reduce unwanted pregnancies around the world^{1,15-20}. Accurate analytical assays are important for development of such drug delivery systems for these contraceptives steroids. Both LNG and ENG are potent therapeutics with effective therapeutic levels below 1 ng/mL in human plasma^{14,21} and

the in vitro release studies for their controlled release formulations often last months or even years. Therefore, ensuring the reliability of in vitro release data during formulation development and clinical batch testing is essential for the safety and efficacy of long-acting release products, and any physical interactions (e.g., adsorption of APIs to laboratory consumables) or chemical instability of the drug that may compromise assays during formulation development is particularly critical.

In this study, we observed significant mass loss of LNG and ENG from solution in various in vitro release settings, prompting us to investigate potential causes. Ruling out chemical instability or precipitation, we ultimately focused on the adsorption of LNG and ENG to common laboratory consumables such as PP tubes and vials. A systematic evaluation was conducted by comparing the adsorption of LNG and ENG to PP and glass consumables in the in vitro release assay, where we also devised a revised assay protocol to minimize the observed adsorption.

Recognizing the implications for more sensitive assay development, we assessed the impact of adsorption on a sensitive liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) assay used for plasma drug analysis. Interestingly, we observed that nylon bags used during release assays could inhibit adsorption, which was likely caused by leachable plasticizer competing for adsorption sites. To evaluate the adsorption directly, we employed atomic force microscopy (AFM) to study the API-PP/glass interface. This study highlights the influence of API adsorption in crucial in vitro and in vivo assays in pharmaceutical development, provides noteworthy reference for LNG and ENG formulation development, complements existing understanding of API adsorption from previous studies, and may offer valuable approaches to improving molecular dynamics models aimed at predicting adsorption.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

Micronized LNG and ENG (purity > 99.9%) were purchased from Chemo Industriale Chimica S.R.L (Saronno, Italy). LNG-d6 was obtained from Cayman Chemical (Ann Arbor, MI, USA). PP microcentrifuge tubes were purchased from Fisher Scientific (Catalog No. 14-666-319). PP vials (Catalog No. 186002639) were procured from Waters (Milford, MA, USA). Glass vials (Catalog No. 50-818-721, 03-452-226), glass inserts (Catalog No. 03-452-339), and screw caps (Catalog No. 03-452-301) were purchased from Fisher Scientific (Hampton, NH, USA). Solvents (LC/MS grade) were also procured from Fisher Scientific.

2.2. Preparation of PLGA-LNG MN patches and PLGA-ENG MPs

PLGA-LNG MN patches were prepared by solvent casting onto silicone molds, as previously described^{16,22}. PLGA/PLA-ENG MPs were prepared using either the solid-oil-water emulsion/solvent evaporation method for one-month release²³ or the coaxial electrospray method for six-month release¹⁵. Chloroform, ethyl acetate, dioxane, tetrahydrofuran, and diglyme were used as organic solvents in the preparation processes.

2.3. In vitro release assays

PLGA-LNG MN patches or PLGA/PLA-ENG MPs, each from the same batch, were gently placed in a 1 μ m pore-size nylon mesh bag (SKU:NMO1FMC, Nylon Monofilament Mesh, Midwest Filter, IL, USA) and then incubated in a predetermined volume of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4, 0.05% (w/v) sodium azide), PBST (PBS pH 7.4, 0.02% (v/v) Tween, 0.05% (w/v) sodium azide), or HEPES (pH 7.4) using PYREX media storage bottles as containers. The nylon mesh bag was utilized to effectively separate the released free drug from the PLGA matrices and LNG/ENG crystals. The PBS volume was calculated to ensure sink conditions (drug concentration < 10% of drug solubility in PBS) throughout the experiments. The setup was

maintained at 37 °C with orbital shaking at 80 rpm (MaxQ SHKE6000, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). At specified time points, 0.5 mL aliquots were sampled from outside the nylon mesh bag in each bottle, and an equal volume of fresh media was added to maintain constant volume.

LNG/ENG concentration in the sampled media was measured using ultra performance liquid chromatography (UPLC) (Acquity, Waters Corp., Milford, MA, USA) equipped with a tunable Ultra-Violet (UV) detector. The mobile phase consisted of a mixture of acetonitrile (ACN) with 0.1% formic acid and water with 0.1% formic acid in a 55:45 (v/v) ratio, at a flow rate of 0.3 mL/min. The injection volume was 10 µL. Separation of LNG/ENG was achieved through a Waters Acquity UPLC Ethylene-Bridged Hybrids (BEH) C18 column (100 mm × 2.1 mm i.d., 1.7 µm particle size) at 50 °C. UV absorbance of LNG/ENG was measured at 245 nm. Calibration standards (1000, 500, 250, 125, 62.5, 31.25, 0 ng/mL in acetonitrile (ACN):water (1:1, v/v)) were prepared from a stock solution of LNG/ENG (1 mg/mL) in a mixture of ACN:water (1:1, v/v) by 1:1 (v/v) serial dilution.

To measure the amount of LNG in PLGA-LNG MN patches, three MN patches from the same batch used in the release study were initially incubated with 10 mL of deionized (DI) water to dissolve the backing consisting of polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) and sucrose. The mixture was then centrifuged at $3,000 \times g$ for 10 min, and the supernatant (water phase) was carefully collected. Next, 10 mL of ACN was added to dissolve the MN pellet, followed by intense vortexing. The solution was then diluted with a 1:1 (v/v) mixture of ACN and water. LNG concentrations in both the water phase and diluted solution were determined using UPLC, as described above. The amount of LNG was calculated based on the measured concentrations, solution volume, and dilution factors. To measure the amount of ENG in PLGA/PLA-LNG MPs, the same protocol used

for quantifying LNG in PLGA-LNG MN patches was followed, except the initial step of adding water and centrifuging was omitted, and 10 mL of acetonitrile was added directly.

The cumulative LNG/ENG release percentages (%) at predetermined time points were calculated as the ratio of the cumulative drug mass released (additive measured concentrations at each time point multiplied by the release media volume) to the total mass of LNG/ENG in the MN patches or MPs.

2.4. Comparison of calibration curves prepared with PP or glass tubes and vials

To prepare a calibration curve of LNG/ENG in PBS (pH 7.4) for UPLC-UV analysis, a stock solution (100 ng/mL) and a series of serial dilutions of LNG/ENG (1000, 500, 250, 125, 62.5, 31.25, and 0 ng/mL) were prepared in either PP or glass tubes. From each tube, 100 μ L of the solution was transferred to either PP or glass vials for injection, which resulted in four calibration curves: g-g (glass tubes transferred to glass vials), g-p (glass tubes to PP vials), p-g (PP tubes to glass vials), and p-p (PP tubes to PP vials). UPLC-UV analysis was performed as previously described¹⁵. Linear calibration was performed by plotting the peak area (μ Au * minutes) against the theoretical concentration, and R-squared value was calculated by linear regression to assess the linearity of the calibration curve.

2.5. Adsorption of LNG/ENG in PBS or ACN:PBS mixture to glass vials

One thousand ng/mL LNG/ENG in PBS or ACN:PBS (1:1, v/v) was prepared again by diluting the 1 mg/mL stock solution of LNG/ENG with the respective solvent in glass tubes. The solutions were then transferred to glass vials and analyzed by UPLC-UV.

2.6. Comparison of calibration curves prepared in ACN:water and ACN:PBS

A series of serial dilutions of LNG/ENG (1000, 500, 250, 125, 62.5, 31.25, and 0 ng/mL) were prepared using either ACN:water (1:1, v/v) or ACN:PBS (1:1, v/v) in either glass or PP tubes.

From each tube, 100 μL of the solution was transferred to either glass or PP vials and then analyzed by UPLC-UV.

2.7. Adsorption of LNG/ENG in PBS or ACN:PBS mixture to PP pipette tips

Solutions of LNG/ENG in PBS or ACN:PBS (1:1, v/v) were prepared in glass vials at concentrations of 31.25 and 62.5 ng/mL. To simulate routine solution handling and assess the interaction between LNG/ENG in the solution and polypropylene pipette tips, 100 μL of the solution was drawn from the vial using a 5–300 μL polypropylene pipette tip (Fisherbrand™ SureOne™, Non-Filtered, Universal Fit, Fisher Scientific, Hampton, NH, USA) and then dispensed back into the same vial. This procedure was repeated one, two, or three times, using a fresh tip for each repetition, or omitted entirely for comparison. The samples in the glass vials were then analyzed by UPLC-UV.

2.8. Quantification of LNG in rat plasma using liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectroscopy

Female Sprague Dawley rat plasma (90 μL , Catalog No. IGRTSDPLAK2E50ML, Innovative Research, MI, USA) was added to either a PP or glass tube. LNG (10 μL) in 1:1 (v/v) methanol:water was spiked into the tube, followed by agitation. Then, 10 μL LNG-d6 (12.5 ng/mL) in 1:1 (v/v) methanol:water was spiked into the tube, followed by agitation. LC-MS grade water (200 μL) was added to the tube, followed by vortexing. The spiked sample was processed by solid phase extraction (SPE). Oasis HLB cartridges (1 mL, 30 mg sorbent, 30 μm , Catalog No. WAT094225, Waters) were installed on a Visiprep™ SPE vacuum manifold (12-port model, Catalog No. 57044, MilliporeSigma). LC-MS grade methanol (1 mL) and water (1 mL) were sequentially pipetted and flowed through each cartridge. One plasma sample was pipetted into a cartridge and slowly flowed through the cartridge using vacuum, followed by 1 mL

methanol:water (5:95, v/v). ACN:methanol (1 mL, 9:1, v/v) was pipetted into the cartridge and collected in a 1.5 mL PP tube after slowly flowing through the cartridge. The collected sample was dried under nitrogen gas at 45 °C using a TurboVap® LV Evaporator. Methanol:water (100 µL, 1:1, v/v) with 0.1% formic acid was added to the tube, followed by vortexing and centrifugation at 12,000 × g for 15 min. The supernatant (50 µL) was collected into a glass insert in a glass vial and stored at 10 °C before LC-MS/MS analysis within 12 h.

The concentration of LNG in the processed sample was measured using liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectroscopy (LC-MS/MS) with a Vanquish LC-TSQ Altis Plus Mass Spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific). A volume of 5 µL of the sample was injected. Liquid chromatography was performed using an Acquity UPLC BEH C18 column (130 Å, 1.7 µm, 2.1 mm × 100 mm) maintained at 60 °C. The mobile phase consisted of water with 0.2 mM ammonium fluoride (phase A) and methanol with 0.2 mM ammonium fluoride (phase B). The flow gradient details are listed in Table S2. For mass spectrometry parameters, ion source settings are detailed in Table S3, the selected reaction monitoring (SRM) settings in Table S4, and the SRM compounds table in Table S5. The calibration curve was generated by correlating the ratios of LNG peak area (counts * min) to the internal standard LNG-d6 peak area with the theoretical concentrations of LNG (ng/mL) using linear regression.

2.9. Effect of nylon bags and plasticizer DIN A on adsorption

In the presence or absence of a nylon bag (FMC Drum Filling Line Filter, 1 Micron, with Flange SKU:NMO1FMC, Midwest Filter LLC, Chicago, IL, USA), a 500 mL PYREX media storage bottle with 500 ng/mL ENG in PBS was placed in a shaking incubator (37 °C, 80 rpm). At designated time points, 500 µL of the solution was sampled into a glass tube, followed by the

addition of 500 μL of ACN and vortex mixing. A 200 μL aliquot was then transferred to a glass vial for UPLC-UV analysis, as described above.

Aliquots of 1 μL of diisononyl adipate (DINA, Purity (GC): mixture of branched chain isomers, Product code: A1387, Lot: 23EDH, TCI America, Portland, OR, USA) were added to 500 mL of PBS prepared in a 500 mL PYREX media storage bottle. Alternatively, a nylon bag, inside which MNs or MPs were placed during in vitro release study, was immersed in the media. In the reference group, no treatment was applied to the bottle with 500 mL PBS. Subsequently, 75 μL of 1 mg/mL LNG in methanol was added to the bottles. The bottles were then shaken (80 rpm) for 1 h at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Following the incubation, 200 μL of the solution was transferred to a glass vial for UPLC-UV analysis, as described above.

2.10. AFM probing of LNG-in-PBS on glass/PP interfaces

Flat fragments of glass and PP were obtained by carefully breaking down glass and PP tubes so that the following surface characterization could be performed on the inner surface. The AFM (Veeco Dimension Icon Atomic Force Microscope, Bruker Corporation, Billerica, MA, USA) was set up within a vibration isolation system and environmental enclosure for high-resolution imaging (noise floor < 0.03 nm RMS). The AFM probe was equipped with a single, V-shaped, Au reflex coated cantilever with a low spring constant, paired with a nominal 2 nm radius tip (SCANASYST-FLUID+, Bruker Nano, Camarillo, CA, USA). A 15 μL drop of PBS or 200 ng/mL LNG in PBS was gently pipetted on the AFM probe as well as the flat fragment of glass or PP. The AFM probe, with its liquid drop, was carefully moved toward the liquid drop on the surface of the flat fragment until the two liquid drops merged. Inside the liquid drop, the probe moved toward the surface, contacted the surface, and then retracted from the surface, during which the interaction forces between the probe and the surface and the surface heights at the tip radius resolution were recorded.

AFM probing to the liquid-PP interface was conducted within 5 min, as evaporation occurred concurrently. Initial AFM probing was performed in a liquid environment without LNG to establish a baseline. This was followed by probing in the presence of LNG, after the same glass or PP fragment used previously was cleaned with LC-MS grade water.

2.11. Statistical analysis

Quantitative data were presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). Statistical analysis and plotting were conducted using GraphPad Prism 10.2.3 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA). Statistical comparisons were performed using either an unpaired two-tailed t-test or one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-hoc test. Results with a p-value of less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant. Sample sizes for each group are specified in the respective figure captions.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Incomplete recovery of contraceptive steroids during in vitro release testing

While developing PLGA MN patches and PLGA MPs encapsulating ENG for controlled release of contraceptive steroids, only ~80% was recovered in the in vitro release study (Figure 1a) of the one-month PLGA-LNG MN patches using PBST as the release media. Despite media replacement (Figure 1b) and changing the media from PBST to PBS (Figure 1c), a 100% mass balance (total released + remaining drug from polymer) was not achieved for the one-month PLGA-LNG MN patches. Similarly, in the development of PLGA-ENG MPs, HEPES buffer was used in addition to PBS during in vitro release, yet a 20% mass loss persisted (Figure 1d). For the six-month PLGA-ENG MPs, the cumulative release curve plateaued at around 60% on day 180, with a mass balance of around 80% (Figure 1e). Overall, a 100% mass balance was not attained in various in vitro

release settings for two different contraceptive steroids (Table 1), and the consistency of these observations suggested that operational error was not a likely explanation.

The potential precipitation of LNG and ENG was considered as a possible cause of the mass loss. The saturation solubility of LNG in PBS at 37 °C was determined to be $4.3 \pm 0.7 \mu\text{g/mL}$. At the termination point of one-month LNG release from PLGA-LNG MN patches in vitro, the concentration was below 500 ng/mL, indicating that precipitation of LNG and ENG due to solution saturation was unlikely under the in vitro release conditions. The potential for conjugation of LNG or ENG to PLGA polymer chains was also investigated as a potential cause of drug mass loss. Should any drug-polymer chemical reaction occur during biodegradation of the PLGA, the conjugated product would be expected to have an altered UV absorbance. To test this hypothesis, forced stability tests were conducted by incubating PLGA-ENG MPs in PBS at various elevated temperatures. However, no multiple peaks or significant shift of peaks were observed on the gel permeation chromatography (GPC)-UV spectra (Figure S1), strongly suggesting that LNG or ENG was not chemically incorporated within PLGA.

Based on further tests and literature reports^{7,9}, adsorption of LNG/ENG to various PP and other material containers and labware was hypothesized to be the cause of the incomplete drug recovery during release evaluation, as described in the sections below.

Figure 1. Observation of mass loss during *in vitro* release evaluation of LNG microneedle patches and ENG microparticles. (a) Set-up of *in vitro* release assay; (b) cumulative release of one-month

LNG microneedle patches in PBST with or without media replacement at each time point; (c) cumulative release of one-month LNG microneedle patches in PBS or PBST without media replacement; (d) cumulative release of one-month ENG microparticles in HEPES or PBS without media replacement; (e) cumulative release of six-month ENG microparticles in PBS with media replacement. N = 3, mean \pm SEM.

Table 1. Mass balance of release curves in Figure 1. N = 3, mean \pm SEM.

	Cumulative release (%) at last time point	Residual drug (%) at last time point	Mass balance (%)
Figure 1b PBST w/o media change	75 \pm 3	9.5 \pm 0.9	84 \pm 3
Figure 1b PBST w/ media change	82 \pm 3	3.2 \pm 0.5	86 \pm 3
Figure 1c PBST w/o media change	69 \pm 4	8.3 \pm 0.9	77 \pm 4
Figure 1c PBS w/o media change	69 \pm 4	11.2 \pm 0.8	80 \pm 4
Figure 1d HEPES w/o media change	66 \pm 5	8.7 \pm 1.0	75 \pm 5
Figure 1d PBS w/o media change	65 \pm 5	13.7 \pm 1.3	78 \pm 5
Figure 1e PBS w/ media change	62 \pm 0.7	17.7 \pm 0.9	79 \pm 2

3.2. Calibration curves prepared with glass and PP containers revealed significant adsorption of LNG/ENG to PP containers in PBS

To investigate the potential adsorption of LNG/ENG in PBS at pH 7.4 to glass and PP containers, we compared calibration curves prepared using different combinations of glass and PP tubes and vials. The preparation involved two steps: serial dilution in a set of tubes, followed by the transfer of aliquots to autosampler vials (Figure 2a). The responses for both LNG and ENG in the p-p (PP tubes to PP vials) group were significantly lower than those in the g-g group. Responses in the p-p group were more than 50% lower than those in the g-g group at low concentrations (Figure 2d, e). Notably, at the lowest concentration (31.25 ng/mL), LNG and ENG were undetectable in the p-p group, indicating significant adsorption to PP, which compromises the lower detection limit of the analytical assay.

The linearity of the calibration curves was also affected by the type of container (Figure 2b, c). The g-g calibration curves for both LNG and ENG showed good linearity, with high R-squared values and low standard deviation of residuals ($Sy.x$)^{24,25} (LNG: R-squared = 0.999, $Sy.x$ = 1014; ENG: R-squared = 0.997, $Sy.x$ = 1728). In contrast, the p-p calibration curves demonstrated poorer linearity with lower R-squared and higher $Sy.x$ (LNG: R-squared = 0.985, $Sy.x$ = 2849; ENG: R-squared = 0.969, $Sy.x$ = 4278). In addition, statistical testing showed that the slopes and intercepts were significantly different ($P < 0.0001$, two-tailed)²⁶.

Comparing LNG and ENG, ENG calibration samples in the p-g group presented much higher response than those in the g-p group, while the difference was smaller than seen with LNG, indicating different adsorption profiles. The observed lower responses and poorer linearity when PP containers were used suggested significant adsorption of LNG and ENG to PP containers, though adsorption of LNG/ENG to glass containers should also be investigated to gain a more detailed understanding.

Figure 2. Comparison of UPLC calibration curves for steroids prepared using PP or glass tubes and vials. (a) Schematic illustration of the preparation of calibration curves; (b) calibration curves

for LNG after g-g (glass tubes to glass vials), g-p (glass to PP), p-g (PP to glass), and p-p (PP to PP) processes; (c) calibration curves of ENG; (d) normalized areas of different concentrations of LNG relative to the g-g group; (e) normalized areas of different concentrations of ENG relative to the g-g group. N = 3 injections, mean \pm SEM.

3.3. Comparison of the adsorption of LNG/ENG to glass containers and PP pipette tips in PBS, ACN:water, and ACN:PBS

Guided by the hypothesis of the different UPLC-UV responses being caused by the differential adsorption of LNG/ENG to glass and PP containers, we set out to explore simple approaches to reduce the adsorption and recover \sim 100% mass balance of LNG/ENG during in vitro release evaluation. After investigating different container materials and alternative sample transfer processes, we focused on changing the solvent of the samples after they were collected from the in vitro release apparatus and transferred into utility tubes, hypothesizing that adding organic solvents may help, as LNG and ENG are highly hydrophobic.

We compared the UPLC-UV responses of LNG/ENG in ACN:water (1:1, v/v) and PBS (pH 7.4). In glass vials, responses of either LNG or ENG in ACN:water (1:1, v/v) were significantly higher than those in PBS (Figure 3a, b). This difference corroborated our hypothesis and led to further comparison of calibration curves prepared in ACN:PBS (1:1, v/v) via g-g or p-p processes. No statistically significant difference was observed between responses of calibration curves prepared in ACN: PBS via either g-g or p-p process at each concentration (Figure 3c, d), in contrast to calibration curves prepared in PBS (Figure 2). It should also be noted that responses of either LNG or ENG in ACN:PBS were higher than those in ACN:water (Figure 3c, d). As PBS has a higher ionic strength than water, the increase of responses may be due to the different electric double

layers on the material surface that would affect the adsorption²⁷, or due to the solvent's influence on molecular polarization and ionization, where differences in dielectric constants between PBS and water could alter how LNG and ENG absorb light²⁸. We therefore concluded that when the same volume of ACN is added to PBS samples from in vitro releases, the calibration samples should also be prepared with ACN:PBS (1:1, v/v).

Given that pipette tips are predominantly made of polypropylene (PP), the observed adsorption of LNG/ENG to PP tubes and vials prompted us to investigate their adsorption to PP pipette tips. To mimic routine laboratory practices during solution preparation, LNG/ENG solutions at low concentrations (31.25 and 62.5 ng/mL) in either PBS or ACN:PBS were prepared in glass vials. A PP pipette tip was then used to draw 100 μ L of the solution, which was dispensed back into the same vial. This procedure, denoted as one contact cycle, was repeated one, two, or three times, each using a new pipette tip, or omitted for comparison (Figure 3e, f). For solutions in PBS, the UPLC-UV responses of both LNG and ENG decreased with increasing contact cycles, indicating adsorption of LNG/ENG to PP pipette tips. This adsorption was positively correlated with the number of contact cycles. Furthermore, LNG exhibited stronger adsorption to PP tips compared to ENG, consistent with the trends observed in Figure 3a, b. At the higher concentration (62.5 ng/mL), the fractional decrease in responses was less pronounced than at lower concentrations (31.25 ng/mL). Additionally, the decrease in responses for ENG was less significant than that for LNG. In contrast, when the solvent was ACN:PBS, no significant differences in UPLC-UV responses were observed regardless of the number of pipette tip contact cycles.

Figure 3. Comparison of the UPLC responses to LNG/ENG reflecting steroid adsorption to glass containers in PBS, ACN:water, and ACN:PBS. (a) Response of LNG (1000 ng/mL) in ACN:water

(1:1, v/v) or PBS (pH 7.4) in glass vials; (b) response of ENG (1000 ng/mL) in ACN:water (1:1, v/v) or PBS (pH 7.4) in glass vials; (c) LNG calibration curves in ACN:water and ACN:PBS after g-g (glass tubes to glass vials) or p-p process; (d) ENG calibration curves in ACN:water and ACN:PBS after g-g (glass tubes to glass vials) or p-p process; (e) adsorption of LNG to PP pipette tips in PBS and ACN:PBS; (f) adsorption of ENG to PP pipette tips in PBS and ACN:PBS. N = 3, mean \pm SEM.

Based on the data above, two points may be worthy of discussion. First, we sought to understand if the addition of ACN to PBS (to form ACN:PBS (1:1, v/v)) reduced adsorption enough to prevent significant mass loss. If there were still adsorption that would lead to significant mass loss, the degree of adsorption would likely be different between g-g and p-p procedures. Since low concentration samples were serially diluted from high concentrations where a higher fractional adsorption would be expected at lower concentrations, any difference in adsorption between the procedures would become more pronounced, resulting in greater divergence between the ACN:PBS g-g and p-p curves at low concentrations in Figure 3c, d. However, no such divergence was observed, indicating that the addition of ACN to PBS reduced adsorption to the extent that whether using PP or glass tubes or vials would not result in significant mass loss. In addition, when the solvent was ACN:PBS, no significant differences in UPLC-UV responses were observed regardless of the number of pipette tip contact cycles. This result indicates that the use of ACN:PBS as a solvent mitigates the adsorption of LNG/ENG to PP pipette tips, further supporting its suitability for calibration and sample preparation in these assays. Furthermore, additional LNG/ENG in vitro release experiments have been conducted (Figure S2) where ACN was added after sampling and a \sim 100% mass balance was recorded.

A second point is that it may be argued that PBS, i.e., the same media used for in vitro release samples, should be used as the solvent for the preparation of calibration curve samples. However, using PBS and PP tubes to prepare the solvent for calibration curve samples reduced the sensitivity of the UPLC-UV assay, because responses of LNG/ENG in PBS and by p-p process were not detected at the lowest concentration as shown in Figure 2d and e. Furthermore, the decrease of measured responses due to adsorption to PP pipette when the solvent was PBS also indicate that PBS should not be used by itself for both the in vitro samples and the calibration curve samples.

To mitigate drug mass loss during the transfer of release samples, we recommend adding an appropriate volume of ACN to inhibit drug adsorption. For example, 500 μL of ACN may be effective for specific scenarios, but the volume should be optimized based on the experimental conditions. Similarly, calibration curve samples should be prepared using the same diluent, e.g., ACN:PBS (1:1, v/v) with 100-1000 μL Gilson® MICROMAN E M1000E positive displacement pipettes, to maintain consistency. In previous experiments comparing calibration curves prepared using either glass or PP, PP tips were uniformly employed with one contact cycle per sample, which should minimize the potential impact of adsorption on the results. Furthermore, in subsequent experiments and the proposed protocol, an ACN:PBS or ACN:water mixture was consistently used for sample preparation at all stages to mitigate the effects of adsorption to PP pipette tips. The validation details (specificity, linearity, range, accuracy, precision, limit of detection, and limit of quantification) of the UPLC-UV methods for both LNG and ENG were provided in Table S1, following the guidelines from International Conference ON Harmonisation (ICH)²⁹.

With the results confirming significant LNG/ENG adsorption to PP labware like tubes, vials, and tips, it is also valuable to contextualize our findings by comparing them with previous studies.

Adsorption of APIs to plastic and glass containers have been reported for many decades, in the clinical setting where researchers raised concerns about the significant reduction of API concentration after interaction of API solution with plastic and glass materials³⁰⁻³². Seminal research since then has studied similar cases in microfluidics using PDMS microdevices⁷ and in vitro cell culture using polystyrene tubes and plates⁴. Specific to this study, a recent study¹ used the steroid API canrenoate as one of the model drugs and observed roughly 10% adsorption to PP tubes when the concentration was at 2 μM (~ 715 ng/mL), while in our study comparing g-g and p-p processes on Figure 2 at the concentration the adsorption difference was around 40%. This might be due to the multiple contact cycles of the solution with the labware during the calibration sample preparation. An earlier study² also monitored the adsorption of several APIs to polystyrene and PP plates and glass vials over time and found that adsorption plateaued after 1 hr. Compared with these previous studies, our study characterized the adsorption of two important contraceptive steroids to PP and glass labware over a range of concentrations and in the more specific calibration curve preparation process. Calibration curves are widely used for the quantification of target materials in various analytical assays. This study highlights the importance of accounting for adsorption effects when developing reliable quantification assays using calibration curves. This consideration is particularly critical in in vitro release evaluations during the development of controlled release systems of highly potent APIs.

3.4. Adsorption of LNG to PP containers may compromise LC-MS/MS assay development

During LC-MS/MS assays to measure the concentration of LNG in rat plasma, we also used PP containers. Given the knowledge of LNG adsorption to PP containers as discussed above, we investigated how this adsorption might affect LC-MS/MS assay results (Figure 4a).

We first confirmed that there was no statistically significant difference between groups using either glass or PP vials before LC-MS/MS analysis. Methanol:water (1:1, v/v) was used to reconstitute LNG after solid-phase extraction from plasma samples, and the reconstituted solution in the same tube was transferred to either a glass or PP vial (Figure 4b). Next, we compared the calibration curves from samples prepared in either glass or PP tubes before solid phase extraction. Though no statistically significant difference was observed between the LNG responses of the two groups (Figure 4c), the differences between the slopes was significant ($P = 0.0007$)²⁶ (Figure 4d). The calibration curve prepared in glass tubes also exhibited a larger R-squared value and lower standard deviation of residuals (Sy.x) (R-squared = 0.9988 and Sy.x = 0.03184), and thus better linearity than the calibration curve prepared in PP vials (R-squared = 0.9739 and Sy.x = 0.1516)^{24,25}. Comparing the %Error in calibration concentrations predicted by the standard curve, calculated by comparing the theoretical value and the value back-calculated by the calibration curve using the y value, the process using glass tubes to prepare samples before solid phase extraction demonstrated better performance than that using PP tubes, especially at lower concentrations (Figure 4e). The results suggest that the adsorption of LNG to PP containers may compromise the development of LC-MS/MS assay that aimed to measure LNG in in vivo samples at very low concentrations. Recent LC-MS/MS assays of LNG and ENG³³⁻³⁵ did not achieve high sensitivity as described here or required the use of much larger amounts of plasma (500 μ L vs 100 μ L). The results to our knowledge are the first example that investigated API adsorption in developing highly sensitive LC-MS/MS methods that are essential in quantifying trace level of APIs and metabolites³⁶, while previous studies concerning API adsorption used LC-UV/Vis methods.

Figure 4. The impact of the adsorption of LNG on LC-MS/MS assay. (a) Brief illustration of the LC-MS/MS development comparing the use of glass or PP tubes before solid phase extraction. (b)

LNG response distribution of processed in vivo samples recovered by methanol:water (1:1, v:v) and then dispensed in PP or glass vials, N = 6; (c) LNG-d6 response distribution of in vivo samples dispensed in PP or glass vials before processing, N = 20; (d) calibration curves of standards prepared in PP or glass vials, N = 3, mean \pm SEM; (e) %Error in standard concentrations predicted by standard curve, N = 3, mean \pm SEM.

3.5. Effect of nylon bags and DINA on LNG/ENG responses in the in vitro release assay

Initially, we hypothesized that the nylon bag used in the in vitro release set-up (Figure 5a), which included a double layer of nylon (polyamide) monofilament mesh and was fully welded with a PP top flange and bottom cap³⁷, might be causing the adsorption of LNG/ENG and thus led to incomplete recovery. To test this, we first compared the behavior of ENG (500 ng/mL in PBS) in the presence and absence of the nylon bag. While the ENG concentration remained stable in glass vessels containing the nylon bag, it decreased over time in vessels without the nylon bag (Figure 5b).

At the same time, the degradation of LNG/ENG was tested as a potential cause of the mass loss. A peak of m/z ($z = +1$) = 398.58 was consistently observed on the LC-MS spectrum from the in vitro release samples (Figure S3). Forced degradation experiments were conducted as previously discussed (), but no degradation was observed. Further examination of the peak and a search of MS databases led to the investigation of diisononyl adipate (DINA, $C_{24}H_{46}O_4$, Mw = 398.6 g/mol) as the potential impurity corresponding to the peak of $m/z = 398.58$ on the LC-MS spectrum.

Having observed the unexpected effect of nylon bag and with the suspicion of the constant impurity being DINA, we hypothesized that DINA, which is commonly used as a plasticizer in polymer systems such as poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC)³⁸ and acrylic sheets³⁹, may have been

introduced into the samples as an adsorption competitor from utility instruments such as the nylon bag. This prompted further study of the effect of DINA on the LNG/ENG responses in the in vitro release setting.

We introduced DINA as a variable in the in vitro release assay as an experimental group. When 1 μ L DINA was added to 500 mL PBS in the release vessel, or when the nylon bag was placed in the vessel, the average response of 150 ng/mL LNG in PBS increased by approximate 9% and 15%, respectively, compared with the control group (Figure 5c). Examination of the UPLC-UV spectra (Figure S4) revealed no differences between samples, indicating that DINA would not alter the LC-UV spectra of the samples. Hence, the presence of materials with leachable components such as plasticizers is an important consideration when evaluating steroid controlled drug release or performing analytical methods.

Recent studies^{9,40,41} characterized adsorption when plasticizers were introduced to polyvinylchloride (PVC) polymer solutions prior to making them into PVC tubing for clinical infusion. Increased sorption was observed, and the researchers discussed the possibilities that adding plasticizers to PVC promoted diffusion of APIs into polymers when plasticizers leached from the polymer increasing free volume in the polymer and polymer chain segmental mobility, or the plasticizers changed the surface property and facilitated adsorption. Our results showed that adsorption decreased in the presence of very low levels of DINA. The contrast may be due to several aspects. As PP is not permeable to such APIs as is PVC, there is no possibility for absorption of the solute into the hydrophobic polymer. The drug (diazepam) and plasticizers (Di-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP), di(ethylhexyl) terephthalate (DEHT), tris(2-Ethylhexyl) Trimellitate (TOTM), and diisononyl cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate (DINCH)) were also different than those used in our study. Levels of plasticizer present at the surface may also be

relevant as in our studies DIN A was only introduced at low enough levels to compete for steroid binding. It is unknown the level to which the plasticizer in the former study was present at the polymer surface.

a

b

c

Figure 5. Effect of plasticizer DINA on the responses of LNG/ENG during in vitro release assay.

(a) Illustration of the in vitro release vessel with nylon bag and the chemical structure of DINA;

(b) normalized ENG concentration with or without nylon bag in the release glass vessel;

(c) responses of 150 ng/mL LNG in PBS (500 mL), with 1 µL DINA in the solution (mean = (1 +

8.96%) \times mean of responses in PBS), or with nylon bag (mean = (1 + 15.1%) \times mean of responses in PBS), N = 6, mean \pm SEM.

3.6. AFM probing revealed adsorption interface

Previous studies employed computational molecular dynamics models to understand the mechanism of adsorption. Sahnoune et al.⁶ applied molecular dynamics to study the adsorption of paracetamol and diazepam to PVC and polyethylene (PE) and suggested that the adsorption was driven by van der Waals interactions. Kemas et al.⁸ studied the effect of physicochemical properties of APIs like acetaminophen on their adsorption to polymer devices made of polydimethyl siloxane (PDMS), polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and other materials. Experimental data, acquired by AFM that were able to profile molecules on surfaces in liquid⁴²⁻⁴⁴ (Figure 6a), may provide more insight into the adsorption mechanism and help build more accurate models predicting adsorption.

Surface roughness was first compared among the samples being glass or PP and with or without LNG. Comparing the PBS-glass (Figure 6b) and PBS-PP (Figure 6d) interfaces without LNG, the PBS-PP interface displayed far more nano-scale structure, indicating higher surface area. When LNG (200 ng/mL) was added (Figure 6c, e), the detailed nano-scale structure was visually found to be smoothed, indicating the adsorption of LNG molecules to the surface and a commensurate reduction in surface area in contact with water. This coating effect was especially obvious in the case of PP (comparing Figure 6e to Figure 6d), which may indicate greater adsorption of LNG to PP containers than to glass. Quantitatively, the Ra (average roughness) and Rq (Root Mean Square (RMS) average roughness) of the glass surface increased when LNG (200 ng/mL) was in the solution, while the PP surface roughness remained similar, although, the distribution of heights

widened after the addition of LNG into the system for both PP and glass (blue plots, Figure 6, c to b, e to d).

The adhesion force between the surface and the tip in the solution environment was also evaluated. The distribution of adhesion force presented a broader and lower peak when LNG was added to the solution contacting the glass, whereas in the case of PP, the adhesion force dramatically increased ~ 100 -fold from pN to nN scale, with clear confirmation of the adsorption of LNG to the PP surface in PBS (Figure 6, g to f, i to h).

The AFM scanning experimentally showed the glass/PP interface with or without LNG in liquid environments. The much more-detailed, small structures observed at the PBS-PP interface may be considered in theoretical modeling to improve future models predicting possible adsorption of molecules without experiment, as a high surface-area provides a large number of binding sites for the drug at the glass or PP solid/PBS interface. It may also suggest that minimizing the nanostructures and making the surface of PP “flatter” on the nanometer scale could potentially help reduce the adsorption of drug molecules to PP, when glass materials are cost-prohibitive or unavailable, or the addition of acetonitrile is not permissible. In addition, the different behavior of adhesion force change between glass (decrease) and PP (dramatic increase) may provide reference experimental data for molecular dynamics simulation⁴⁵.

In our specific system, adsorption is most certainly driven by the hydrophobic effect⁴⁶, wherein the highly hydrophobic steroid APIs ($\log P > 3$ ^{47,48}) interacts with the nanostructured polypropylene (PP) surface in aqueous PBS. The covering of hydrophobic cavities and grooves of the PP surface with steroid (evidenced by AFM topography) likely minimize energetically unfavorable contacts between water and the nonpolar drug molecules, promoting adsorption^{49,50}. This is consistent with the observed reduction in surface area post-adsorption, indicating the entropically driven

displacement of water from the nanostructured hydrophobic interface to gain full mobility of the solvent. The hydrophobic effect may be further enhanced by weak van der Waals forces between the nonpolar steroid APIs and the polypropylene surface, as ionic or electronic interactions are negligible in the PBS environment. To reduce such interactions and thus mitigate adsorption, strategies such as adding surface active amphiphilic organic solvents (e.g., ACN) for hydrophobic interaction², modifying surfaces to increase hydrophilic by plasma treatment, ultraviolet radiation treatment, alkali treatment, or hydrophilic polymers coating for hydrophobic interaction⁵¹, and adding salts for ionic interaction², have been suggested.

The current study applied material characterization techniques, such as AFM, to provide experimental evidence of drug adsorption at the PP and glass interfaces. Though inspired by previous studies that used AFM to characterize molecules^{43,44}, our work may complement existing studies^{1,6} that used computational modeling or focused on the characteristics of the APIs. Beyond simple analysis of adsorption phenomenon this work examines how material properties (e.g., the presence of plasticizers within materials useful for in-vitro release studies) can complex the adsorption behavior and the impact of adsorption on quantification assays (e.g., the highly sensitive LC-MS/MS assay for Levonorgestrel in rat plasma) important for pharmaceutical development. These findings provide actionable guidelines for considering apparatus materials and handling procedures to ensure accurate in vitro release profiles, which are essential in evaluating drug delivery systems. These insights are of applied nature to the active development of long-acting contraceptive systems^{17,52,53}, where a long-acting contraception dosage form can remain effective in the patients for months or years and the accurate measurement of contraceptive steroids such as LNG and ENG during the pharmaceutical development process before their clinical trials in human subjects is essential in safeguarding productivity health⁵⁴⁻⁵⁶.

Figure 6. AFM probing of the PBS-glass/PP interface with and without LNG in liquid mode. (a) Schematic illustration of the AFM experiment: height was measured by detecting the vertical movement (ramping) of the cantilever as it maintained constant force while scanning the surface, and adhesion force was measured at the E stage. Height sensor: (b) distribution (%) of heights (top) and visualization (bottom) of PBS-glass interface; (c) distribution (%) of heights (top) and

visualization (bottom) of PBS-glass interface in the presence of 200 ng/mL LNG; (d) distribution (%) of heights (top) and visualization (bottom) of PBS-PP interface; (e) distribution (%) of heights (top) and visualization (bottom) of PBS-PP interface in the presence of 200 ng/mL LNG. Adhesion: (f) distribution (%) of adhesion force (top) and visualization (bottom) of PBS-glass interface; (g) distribution (%) of adhesion force (top) and visualization (bottom) of PBS-glass interface in the presence of 200 ng/mL LNG; (h) distribution (%) of adhesion force (top) and visualization (bottom) of PBS-PP interface; (i) distribution (%) of adhesion force (top) and visualization (bottom) of PBS-PP interface in the presence of 200 ng/mL LNG. Ra: arithmetic average roughness, Rq: RMS average roughness⁵⁷.

4. Conclusions

This study presents a systematic investigation into the adsorption of two widely used contraceptive steroids LNG and ENG to common research consumables during development of controlled-release dosage forms. We explored the impact of adsorption phenomena on formulation development and provided preliminary mechanistic understanding of the adsorption process. The approximately 20% incomplete recovery of LNG and ENG during in vitro release studies while developing PLA/PLGA microparticles and microneedles encapsulating ENG or LNG, respectively, was shown to be due to the adsorption of LNG and ENG to PP containers in PBS, excluding other investigated causes such as precipitation of the hydrophobic LNG and ENG in PBS and potential degradation during long-term release.

For the in vitro release protocol using UPLC-UV to measure API concentration, calibration curves were prepared using both glass and PP consumables. The results indicated significant adsorption of LNG and ENG to PP materials, which likely caused poorer linearity and a higher

limit of detection. This compromised the lower limit of the UPLC-UV assay, as the lowest measurable concentrations achievable with glass materials were not observed with PP materials. Extended experiments using ACN:water/PBS revealed that there was still adsorption of LNG and ENG to glass in PBS, and in this specific protocol the same volume of ACN was added to samples after they were collected from in vitro release to help mitigate the compromising effect of adsorption.

Realizing the adsorption of LNG, for in vivo experiments we also performed the comparison of glass and PP tubes while preparing calibration curve samples in the LC-MS/MS method that aimed to measure LNG concentration in rat plasma at very low concentrations. Though no statistically significant difference was observed comparing the responses of samples prepared in either glass or PP containers, the calibration curve by glass was better than that by PP and the benefit of using glass was even clearer when comparing the deviation of calculated concentrations from theoretical concentrations, indicating the potential complexity introduced by the adsorption effect. Additionally, plasticizer contamination from nylon bags used in the release assay, likely from DINA, was found to influence LNG/ENG responses in both PP and glass containers, emphasizing the importance of managing plasticizer contamination to avoid skewing results during in vitro release studies. Finally, AFM was employed to study the interface of LNG in PBS and glass/PP materials. The coating effect after the addition of LNG into the system corroborated the adsorption theory. At the same time, the surface morphology difference between glass and PP materials revealed by AFM suggests that the surface roughness and actual surface area exposed to the solution should be considered more carefully in addition to the properties of the APIs. Hence, this study may be an important reference for researchers developing high-sensitivity assays, as it was

for us during assay development initially without accounting for adsorption, particularly for those developing new long-acting release systems for contraceptive hormones.

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Author Contributions

T.Z. contributed to the conceptualization of the study, performed the majority of the experimental work, data collection, and analysis, and drafted the manuscript. A.D., J.T., and R.S. assisted with experimental design, data interpretation, and manuscript revision. J.Y.C. and M.R.P. provided expertise in dosage form preparation and assisted with manuscript preparation and editing. S.P.S. supervised the overall research, provided critical guidance throughout the study, assisted with manuscript preparation and editing, and was responsible for correspondence regarding the manuscript. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Supporting Information

SI_LNG_ENG_adsorption.pdf: GPC-UV spectra of PLGA microparticles loaded with ENG after forced stability tests, cumulative release of LNG PLGA MNPs in PBS (pH 7.4), suspected degradation product on LC-MS spectra, UPLC-UV spectra of LNG in PBS in glass vials, validation details of LNG/ENG UPLC-UV methods, LC-MS/MS flow gradients and optimized settings.

Notes

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